

INTERACTIVE APPROACHES OF LEARNING AND TEACHING SPEAKING

*Sh. Ashurov¹, D. Qurbonova²**Abstract:*

Learning and teaching foreign languages through speaking is an urgent issue nowadays. It is known that it is connected with other skills. Additionally, speaking skills, for example, the English language has been considered as the most challenging of the four skills giving the information that it involves a complex process of constructing meaning. This requires speakers to decide about why, how and when to communicate depending on the cultural and social context in which the speaking act occurs.

Key words: Process, skills, interactive, approaches.

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English language is universal and unique. Learning an international language is essential due to globalization in many spheres, as the number of individuals using English for communication nowadays far outnumbers those who speak it as their native language. Up to the end of the 1960s the field of language learning was influenced by environmentalist ideas that paid attention to the learning process as being conditioned by the external environment rather than by human internal mental process. Furthermore, mastering series of structures in a linear way was paramount [1]. The majority of kindergarten-aged children still lack writing and reading skills, but they can pick up new language skills through listening, or the audiolingual teaching style. By following a set sequence of listening, writing, reading, and speaking for every structure, the teaching approach placed an emphasis on teaching vocal abilities first rather than written ones. By the late 1960s, the previous view of learning to speak as a mechanical process consisting in the oral repetition of grammatical structures was challenged by Chomsky's theory of language development (Chomsky's theory of language development). The emphasis on practicing exercises and repeating grammatical structures advocated by the audio lingual approach was replaced by "an interest in cognitive methods with would enable language structures and grammatical patterns" [2]. The next approach is called interaction way. People who try to learn or teach in native atmosphere or covered with professional people can get the best result in future. Also thinking in foreign language can help according to it.

Adopting interactive teaching methodology in the language classroom is the only way to make the learners get motivated and enthusiastic in the learning process. Interactive teaching styles incorporate a multitude of goals beneath a single roof. Interactive classes are designed around a simple principle: without practical application, students often fail to comprehend the depths of the study material. Pair work, group work and teamwork are not identical terms. Pair work requires organization of the learners on the part of the teacher and it can be activated in all the classrooms, for instance - a student may be asked to work with the student near him/her; or it may be between students of equal proficiency; or as per the situation and the task demands. Group work, by nature, is a more complex structure as it requires the performance of the learners in different roles assigned to them especially of communicative and interactive setting as well as a certain amount of physical reorganization

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of the classroom. One of the useful teaching approaches used in improving speaking skills is interactive teaching strategy. Interactive teaching is a strategy that supports self-learning of student during the process as well as their development by engaging them with their peers. You should support active engagement of learners in the class communication process for effective learning. This study focused on the effects of interactive teaching strategy on the improvement of speaking skills of students learning English as a second language. A pre- and post-test based experimental design was employed in this study with a control and an experiment group. The participants of the study consist of A1 level pupils who are enrolled in learning English. Speaking skills of pupils should be measured with "Speaking Skills Evaluation Scale" and "Sources of Speaking Anxiety Scale." Interactive teaching strategy improves the speaking skills of students learning English as a second language.

Getting Beginners to speak is often not too difficult. Simple exercises and repeating phrases and dialogues are key notes. However, what if you want your learners to produce English, not merely verbally fill in the blanks or read out sentences from your textbook? Focus on getting a message across. At this stage in their learning, the vocabulary and grammar knowledge of your students is still quite limited, but that doesn't mean they can't communicate. Give your students real-life scenarios (introducing themselves, going shopping) and let them role-play using verbal and non-verbal communication with a focus on communicating and delivering a message, not correctness. Let them make liberal use of visual aids. They might be surprised how much they can communicate with a few words. Take a look at Poodll's mini lessons for easily implemented speaking activities.

As always, the British Council has a great selection of speaking exercises for the beginner's level. For more tips on how to teach speaking to beginners, take a look at this video.

Practicing speaking with intermediate learners can be difficult. At this stage, students are often aware of their mistakes and perceived shortcomings and might feel shy or inhibited. Much like when teaching beginner students, the goal should be on getting a message across. A communication situation is successful if all parties understand each other, not if they speak with perfect grammar and pronunciation. Help your students let go of the idea of perfection. Encourage your students to use varied vocabulary. Instead of simple words like "good", "bad", or "very", ensure that they challenge themselves and use appropriate synonyms.

Poodle uses its in-built transcription feature which transcribes and evaluates your students' speech and supports them with their pronunciation and fluency. Take a look at our interactive transcript player for an easy speech-teaching solution.

Teaching advanced students is both rewarding and challenging. At this level, students usually have a good command over vocabulary and grammar issues, expanding the topics you can discuss in your classroom as well as the complexity of the material. Debate clubs, role-plays, and even creating short films or podcasts are great ways to teach speaking at this level.

One of the hypotheses expressed the view that some teachers might fail in teaching speaking skills because their assumptions about how languages are acquired and what features influence the way spoken production is composed prevent them from teaching the right skills.

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